

Development of a High-Efficiency and Compact Contra-Rotating Rim-Driven Propulsor

Kazuki Hosono^{1,*}, Takuyoshi Yamada¹, Shigeki Senoo¹ and Takehiko Nishida¹

¹ Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Ltd., Japan

Abstract. Rim-driven propulsors (RDPs) have emerged as an innovation in electrified marine propulsion systems, particularly due to their zero greenhouse gas emissions. These systems feature a permanent magnet synchronous motor integrated within the duct of a ducted propeller. This configuration allows the motor to drive the propeller directly from the peripheral rim. One of the primary advantages of RDPs is the liberation of internal space within the vessel. By eliminating the need for a motor to be installed inside the ship, this design maximizes the available space for cargo and other essential equipment. Additionally, RDPs are more compact than traditional POD-type propulsors. However, integrating the motor into the duct presents challenges. The design must adhere to specific constraints: the propeller and motor must share key specifications, such as rotational speed, diameter, and axial length. Consequently, the input torque generated by the motor must match the torque required by the propeller, making the design of a highly efficient RDP a complex endeavor. To optimize overall efficiency, a design system has been established to concurrently assess both propulsion efficiency and motor efficiency, maximizing what is defined as system efficiency. A prototype of the 8kW contra-rotating RDP (CR-RDP) was successfully designed and manufactured. Its propulsion efficiency was evaluated through towing tank tests with systematically varying towing speed and rotational speed. Measurement results taken during these experiments indicated that the propulsion efficiency of the CR-RDP exceeded that of both a ducted propeller and an open propeller as reported in the existing literature.

Keywords: Rim-driven propulsors (RDP), Contra-rotating propeller (CRP), Design system, Tank test

1 Introduction

In recent years, due to growing concerns about global warming, there has been increasing attention on improving the efficiency of ships, which account for a few percent of global greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, regulations on greenhouse gas emissions, such as the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI), have been enforced, and shipbuilders and marine machinery manufacturers are competing in research and development to improve efficiency and build alternative fuel applications. Furthermore, some ships are now aiming to achieve zero emissions by using electric motor-driven propellers powered by batteries, avoiding the use of fossil fuels, and paving the way for fully electric ships.

Focusing on the propulsion systems of ships, the combination of rotating blades and prime movers such as diesel engines and motors basically accounted for most of the research and development, and this trend is expected to continue in the near future. Among them, rim-driven propulsors (RDP: Rim-Driven Propulsor or RDT: Rim-Driven Thruster), which innovatively combine rotating blades and prime movers, have been developed and commercialized by several manufacturers. This has a mechanism in which the ring part, called the rim of a conventional ring-propeller, is integrated with the rotor of the motor, and the stator of the motor is installed on its outside of the ring part. This propulsor has a high affinity for the propeller with duct or nozzles, and the side thruster with structure on the outer periphery.

The concept of rim-driven propulsors dates back to the patent by Kort[1] in 1936, and several research projects have been carried out since around 2000. For example, Bill Van Blarcom et al [2]. conducted tank tests and demonstrated that rim-driven propulsors potentially may have better propulsion efficiency than conventional propulsors and may reduce hull shape constraints due to their smaller size compared to POD-type azimuth thrusters. In addition, Stephen A. Huyer et al. [3] showed that this technology could be applied to pump-jet propulsors and presented examples of optimizing the duct shape under the constraints of motor with computational fluid dynamics (CFD). Steven Fletcher et al. [4] summarized the characteristics, promising applications, technical challenges, and future prospects of rim-driven propulsors in the article.

* Correspondence to: kazuki.hosono.kw@mhi.com

Summarizing previous research and development, the general advantages of rim-driven propulsors are as follows:

- Reduction of hull shape constraints due to more compact propulsion unit
- Reduction of propulsor and ship layout constraints due to electrification
- Ease of multiple propulsor arrangement and replacement (only connection of power supply cable to the hull)
- High quietness
- External water cooling eliminates the need for a motor cooling system

On the other hand, similar to a ring propeller, it is expected that friction losses at the rotating outer rim would be significant.

The authors focused on the fact that rim-driven propulsors do not require a drive shaft and considered them highly compatible with contra-rotating propellers. However, the mechanism is different from that of the conventional propellers, and the design and manufacturing methods would be complicated. Therefore, the design and manufacturing method of the Contra-Rotating Rim-Driven Propulsor (CR-RDP) was planned, and the fluid characteristics were obtained by the towing tank test with the 8-kW prototype.

2 Consideration of the Design Concept

The cross-sectional view of the Contra-Rotating Rim-Driven Propulsor (CR-RDP) is shown in Figure 1. In the rim-driven propulsor, the ring called the rim on the peripheral side of the propeller blades serves as the rotor of the motor, and permanent magnets are attached on it. The coils serving as the stator of the motor are placed on structures such as ducts on the outside of the rim. This propulsion system directly drives the rim on the outer periphery of the propeller through the rotating magnetic field generated by the current flowing through the coils. Therefore, it is suitable for applications such as a ducted propeller and tunnel/side thrusters, which have structures on the outer periphery of the propeller. Additionally, since the propeller's rim is directly driven by the motor, it does not require a drive shaft, unlike conventional shaft-driven propellers. Although the thickness of the duct increases due to the built-in motor, the overall length in the axial direction can be significantly shortened. Furthermore, in this study, sensorless control has been applied, allowing the propulsor to be driven simply by connecting the power supply cable to the propulsion unit. These features make it easier to adopt contra-rotating propellers (CRP), which have not been widely adopted due to the complexity of the drive shaft mechanism. Therefore, utilizing these structural advantages, this study adopted the concept of a Contra-Rotating Rim-Driven Propulsor (CR-RDP), which is expected to achieve high propulsion efficiency.

Figure 1. Cross-section of Rim-Driven Propulsor

3 Propulsor Design

Based on the concept determined in the previous section, the design of the Contra-Rotating Rim-Driven Propulsor (CR-RDP) was carried out. For rim-driven propulsors, the main design variables for both the motor and the propeller, such as diameter: D_m and D_p , axial length: L , and rotational speed: N , must be shared. The effects of these design variables on the motor and propeller efficiency are summarized in Table 1. Due to the complex effects of these design variables on both efficiencies, it was considered difficult to achieve an optimal design using

conventional design methods. A design system for simultaneously designing the motor and propeller configurations was constructed. The system optimizes the system efficiency by multiplying the motor efficiency and the propeller efficiency under the required conditions. Figure 2 shows an outline of this design system. This design system consists of an outer loop that maximizes system efficiency and inner loops that meet the performance requirements of the motor and propeller.

For the motor part, the torque and efficiency obtained from the main design variables under the initial motor current condition are evaluated using the motor performance evaluation model constructed from the previous design results. The motor current is estimated using the calculated torque, and if there is a difference from the target motor power, the motor current is adjusted and re-estimated to match the target power, and the performance of the motor producing the target power is evaluated.

For the propeller part, in addition to the main design variables of diameter, axial length, and rotational speed, the propeller shapes are created using 36 parameters that control the number of blades and three-dimensional blade shapes for the fore and aft propellers. The duct shape is also simultaneously modified within the range that can enclose the motor with five parameters. After that, the performance is evaluated with CFD. If there is a discrepancy with the target power, the pitch is adjusted and re-evaluated to match the target power, and finally the performance of the propeller producing the target power is re-evaluated.

By optimizing the main design variables of diameter, axial length, and rotational speed, as well as the parameters related to the propeller and duct shapes using an optimization algorithm, the shape and principal items that maximize system efficiency can be calculated. Figure 3 shows some of the results from the design system. Multiple characteristic curves are drawn for the main design variables of diameter: D , axial length: L , and rotational speed: N . It was found that motor efficiency improves with longer axial length, larger diameter at the same rotational speed, and higher rotational speed at the same diameter. On the other hand, the propeller efficiency improves with shorter axial length, smaller diameter at the same rotational speed, and lower rotational speed at the same diameter. In addition, the propeller blades exported from the design system had a load distribution which had also loads at the blade tip, unlike conventional open propellers. The blade tips are connected to the rim, which is expected to prevent tip vortex and leakage losses.

For these reasons, the principal items shown in Table 2 were selected, which have a large diameter and low rotational speed, and have the best system efficiency.

Table 1. Summary of the effects of design variables on motor and propeller

	Motor	Propeller
Motor diameter: D_m Propeller diameter: D_p	If it is large: ✓ ↓ Motor torque → ↓ Copper loss	If it is large: ✓ ↓ Momentum loss → ↑ Efficiency ✗ ↑ Surface area → ↑ Friction loss
Axial length: L	If it is large: ✓ ↓ Current density → ↓ Copper loss	If it is large: ✗ ↑ Surface area → ↑ Friction loss
Rotational speed: N	If it is small: ✓ ↓ Speed → ↓ Iron & windage loss ✗ ↑ Motor torque → ↑ Copper loss	If it is small: ✓ ↓ Tip speed → ↓ Friction loss

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of RDP design system

Figure 3. Output results from RDP design system

Table 2. Principal items of CR-RDP

Power	4 kW x 2 stage = 8 kW
Rotational speed	246 rpm
Design ship speed	4.21 m/s
Motor rotor – Inner diameter	450 mm
Motor rotor – Outer diameter	475.9 mm
Motor axial length	85 mm for each
Types of motor	3 phases, 30 poles IPMSM
Propeller diameter	440 mm
Propeller Pitch Ratio (P/D)	fore: 3.9857 aft: 3.0968
Propeller boss diameter	90 mm
Num. of blades	fore: 6 aft: 5

4 Fluid and Structural Design

Based on the shape from the design system in the previous section, detailed design was carried out to achieve further high efficiency while considering manufacturability.

The shape of the propellers was improved in the detailed design based on the shape obtained from the design system. The rotational speed and power of the propeller blades were designed to be the same in the fore and aft propellers, and the swirling flow at the outlet was successfully eliminated. This effect was significant due to the large propeller loading coefficient condition set as the design operating point, and it was expected to improve the efficiency by about 7.5% [6] compared to conventional single-stage open propellers.

Additionally, one of the advantages of rim-driven propulsors is "high quietness," which is attributed to the effects of electrification and the lower rotational speed compared to conventional propulsors. In this study, to take advantage of this, a low rotational speed configuration was selected, and the propeller blades shape such as load distribution, blade surface area and the duct internal flow path were designed to prevent cavitation within the design operating range. Specifically, the duct shape was modified based on the initial shape, considering cavitation and manufacturability. Since the duct thrust is generated at the suction part near the leading edge, the internal flow path before the fore propeller was designed as a converging flow path, while the flow path behind it was designed as a constant cross-section. An easy way to improve the efficiency is to increase the thrust of the duct. However, if the thrust at the leading edge of the duct is increased, cavitation may occur at the leading edge, and even if it does not, the pressure near the propellers lowers and the risk of cavitation increases. How to balance the propulsion performance and cavitation performance is a key point for designing the CR-RDP. This design avoids the pressure drop caused by converging flow, which can lead to cavitation, and also considers manufacturability by allowing the same motor to be used for both the fore and aft propellers by keeping the propeller diameter the same. Additionally, the duct was designed with a three-part structure in the axial direction for manufacturability. To prevent enlarging the duct thickness for the bolt fastening, the fastening parts were covered with fairings to minimize the fluid resistance and to minimize the efficiency degradation due to manufacturing.

The thrust generated by the propeller is transmitted to the fixed shaft through water-lubricated sliding bearings installed on the inner shaft. For small thrusters, rim-driven thrusters without a fixed shaft have been commercialized. However, it has been considered that having a fixed shaft is more advantageous from the perspective of vibration and strength than having a bearing within a built-in motor which means the bearing system becoming more complicated. For example, if there is no fixed shaft, the propeller blade is cantilevered from the outer rim, and vibration and deformation of the blade must be considered. The thrust transmitted to the fixed shaft is transferred to the duct through fore and aft struts installed before and after the propellers. Considering the number of blades in the fore and aft, four struts were adopted in an uneven arrangement. Finally, the combined thrust from the propeller and the duct is transmitted to the ship hull through the upper strut. From the point of view of fluid performance, it is desirable for the duct and upper strut to be an integrated structure, but for manufacturability, a divided structure was adopted.

The motor employed a direct water-cooling system shown in Figure 4 as schematic diagram. This eliminates the need for some auxiliary equipment such as the cooling water pump, which simplifies the system and improves

system efficiency by reducing auxiliary power. There is a gap between the stator and rotor of the motor, and water flows through this gap to promote cooling. When the propeller blades rotate, a pressure difference is created between the front and back side of this gap. Utilizing this pressure difference, water flows from the high-pressure area to the low-pressure area. Since this flow may reduce the propeller efficiency caused by friction losses on the gap surface, this effect was evaluated in the next section. Figure 5 shows the shape of the 8kW prototype designed with manufacturability.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of direct water-cooling system

Figure 5. 3D drawings of CR-RDP

5 Performance Evaluation by Computational Fluid Dynamics

In order to evaluate the fluid performance of the designed CR-RDP, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation was conducted. ANSYS CFX (2021R2) was used for this simulation. The SST $k-\omega$ model is used as the turbulence model, and the effect of turbulence transition is also considered because the Reynolds number, calculated using the tip speed and chord length of the propeller blades, was approximately 5×10^5 . The simulation type was unsteady to evaluate the phase angle effects of the struts and the fore and aft propeller.

Figure 6 shows the time-averaged pressure distribution on the propulsor surface and time-averaged streamlines on the cross-section of the rotating axis at the design operating point. It was confirmed that the contra-rotating propellers eliminated the swirl flow at the propulsor exit. Furthermore, the bolt fairing for manufacturability did not adversely affect the overall flow. The suction streamline almost passed through the duct leading edge, and the discharge streamline didn't change from the duct exit. Therefore, it was confirmed that the design of the duct internal flow path was appropriate.

Figure 7 shows the thrust and power of the propulsor at the design rotational speed concerning ship speed. The thrust at the design point: 4.21 m/s was approximately 1200 N, and the power was about 7.6 kW. Although this is 5% less than the rated power of 8.0 kW, it was designed to be slightly smaller in consideration of the need to prevent torque overload at maximum power during tank tests. During the tank tests, the rotational speed was increased by about 2% from the design rotational speed to obtain the rated power. When operating at a constant power, the thrust increases as the ship speed decreases, and the thrust could be more than 3000 N under bollard conditions, meaning zero ship speed. On the other hand, it was confirmed that the power did not change significantly even if the ship speed decreased from the design point. This indicates that it is possible to increase

the rotational speed from zero to the rated speed without significantly increasing the power from the rated value, which could produce large thrust and suggests good acceleration performance.

Figure 8 shows the thrust distribution ratio generated by the propeller blades, duct, boss, and other appendages such as struts. The total thrust was normalized at the design point thrust. It was found that the increase of the thrust in the low ship speed range was significantly influenced by the duct and boss. The increase in the propeller thrust was small even when the ship speed decreased, and it corresponded to the almost constant power. On the other hand, it was found that the duct and boss became a resistance at the high ship speed. This means that it is important to design the duct shape appropriately according to the operating condition.

Figure 9 compares the efficiency against the propeller loading coefficient with a typical nozzle propeller [6] and the ideal efficiency obtained from one-dimensional momentum theory. It is confirmed that the efficiency is higher than that of a typical nozzle propeller in all operating ranges.

Based on the CFD results, the losses in each part were analyzed and shown in Figure 10. The energy input from the fore and aft propellers is shown on the left, and the energy given to the fluid is analyzed and shown on the right. It was found that 65% was given as thrust work, which corresponds to the propeller efficiency. Additionally, momentum loss, representing the momentum discharged to the outflow, accounted for 17%. Momentum loss was calculated from the propeller loading coefficient and obtained from one-dimensional momentum theory. Next, losses around the propeller blades and due to appendages were evaluated. Since the swirl flow from the propulsor outlet was small, swirl flow loss was close to zero. Friction losses on the propeller surface and the rim surface in the main flow path accounted for most of the losses around the propeller blades, and friction losses and gap flow losses in the rim gap were small. This was the result of reducing the rim friction losses by lowering the rotational speed. Next, performance degradation due to appendages was calculated by comparing CFD results with and without appendages. It was confirmed that the increase in losses due to bolt fairings was almost zero and it was shown to be well designed. It was found that the upper strut accounted for a large portion of the strut loss. It was considered that the split structure of the duct and upper strut for manufacturability and the addition of the upper strut connecting part were factors contributing to the increase in losses.

The effect of duct suction condition on propulsion efficiency is summarized in Figure 11. At the design point, the duct suction area is appropriate, and the efficiency and cavitation performance are well balanced. When the propeller loading coefficient decreases, meaning the rotational speed decreases relative to the advance speed, the suction capacity of the propeller decreases and the suction area of the duct decreases. This state is shown in the figure on the left. The duct creates drag, but the cavitation performance is improved. On the other hand, when the propeller loading coefficient increases, meaning the rotational speed increases relative to the advance speed, the suction capacity of the propeller increases and the suction area of the duct increases. This state shown in the figure on the right. The duct creates thrust, but the cavitation performance is decreases.

Figure 6. Pressure on CR-RDP ($V_{\text{ship}} = 4.21 \text{ m/s}$, $N = 246 \text{ rpm}$)

Figure 7. Thrust and power performance of CR-RDP (CFD, $N = 246 \text{ rpm}$)

Figure 8. Breakdown of thrust force (CFD, N = 246 rpm)

Figure 9. Comparison of efficiencies (N = 246 rpm)

Figure 10. Loss breakdown chart of CR-RDP ($V_{ship} = 4.21$ m/s, N = 246 rpm)

Figure 11. Effect of duct suction on propulsion efficiency

6 Manufacturing and Onshore Test Run

The manufacturing of the CR-RDP was carried out. Aluminum alloys, A5000 or A6000 series, were used based on the viewpoint of corrosion resistance in underwater environment. Additionally, particularly around the propeller blades, it was necessary to manage the gap distance between the rotor and stator of the motor, so residual stress was removed during material manufacturing to reduce distortion during manufacturing processes. Furthermore, to improve underwater reliability, chromic acid anodizing was applied to all parts, and the bolted joints were insulated with silicone sealant to prevent electrochemical corrosion.

Figure 12 shows the prototype CR-RDP manufactured in this study. Finally, a low-speed test run was conducted onshore, and it was confirmed that the rotational speed measured with a non-contact tachometer was the same as that according to the sensorless control command. As described above, it was confirmed that there was no problem in manufacturing. Tank tests would be conducted from the next chapter.

Figure 12. CR-RDP in ground trial run

7 Verification Test Method

Due to the structure of the CR-RDP, which is directly driven by the motor from the outer rim, the propeller thrust and torque cannot be measured with conventional dynamometers. Additionally, since there is no drive shaft, direct measurement of the propeller thrust and torque is also difficult. Therefore, the thrust generated by all fluid components such as propellers, duct, boss and struts were measured in this study. The torque of the propellers was evaluated by the measured motor input power and recalculated using the characteristic map of the rim-driven motor created on the motor test bench. The appearance of the motor test bench and the characteristic map obtained there are shown in Figure 13.

The tank tests were conducted in a towing tank. The towing tank has a total length of 285 meters and is equipped with a towing carriage to tow the test model. The test items included four items: bollard tests to evaluate the bollard pull/push performance when mounted on tugboats, propulsion performance tests, oblique towing tests assuming steering with an azimuth mechanism, and long-term health tests to confirm sufficient cooling of the motor with the direct water-cooling system.

In the bollard tests, the propulsor was mounted to the tank via the towing carriage, and the propeller was operated to evaluate the propulsor thrust and torque. In propulsion performance tests, the propulsor was mounted to the towing carriage and towed while rotating the propeller to evaluate the propulsor thrust and torque. Next, in the oblique towing tests, the propulsor was mounted at an angle to the forward direction of the towing carriage and towed while rotating the propeller to evaluate the axial force which is parallel to the propulsor rotating axis, the

lateral force which is perpendicular to the rotating axis, the yaw moment around the upper strut, and propeller torque. Finally, in the health tests, the propulsor was operated for a long time in the bollard condition, and motor temperature changes were measured to confirm the effectiveness of the direct water-cooling system.

Figure 13. Rim-driven motor test bench and motor characteristics map

8 Measurement Method

Figure 14 shows an image and a photograph of the propulsor arrangement during the measurement in the towing tank. The five-component force/torque sensor (F_x , F_y , M_x , M_y , M_z) was installed between the towing carriage and the propulsor. In addition, an open boat was installed to prevent wave generation. The open boat was supported separately from the measurement system to ensure that the resistance on the open boat didn't affect the measured force/torque of the propulsor. This method allowed the measurement of the fluid force acting only on all underwater fluid components of the propulsor, such as the propellers, duct, boss, and struts.

An azimuth mechanism was installed between the towing carriage and the five-component force/torque sensor to allow setting the azimuth angle during oblique towing tests. Additionally, an adjustable jig was also prepared to adjust the height relationship between the towing carriage and the propulsor. During the bollard tests, the hull of the open boat was submerged to avoid air suction vortex, and while in the propulsion performance tests and the oblique towing tests, the hull of open boat was not submerged. The submersion depth I was set to $I/D_p = 1.332$ in the bollard tests and $I/D_p = 1.3$ in the propulsion performance tests and oblique towing tests. In tank tests, the inflow velocity to the propulsor could change due to the residual flow from the previous run. Therefore, in this test, sufficient time intervals were taken between runs, and the ground speed was measured as the advance speed. Repeated measurements under several conditions confirmed that the time intervals were sufficient.

Figure 15 shows the control system of the propulsor. Power was supplied from two sets of lithium-ion batteries (rated voltage 48 V, capacity 7.2 kWh/set) mounted on the towing carriage via an inverter. It is assumed that power will be supplied from batteries when installed on a ship, and this test aimed to confirm the technical challenges in such a scenario. Since the motor does not have a main shaft and position detection using a resolver is not possible, sensorless control was applied to the motor. In addition, during preliminary onshore operation tests, it was confirmed that the control command of rotational speed from the inverter matched the actual measured value by a non-contact tachometer. For these reasons, the actual operating rotational speed was not measured during the test, and the performance evaluation was conducted using the command rotational speed. In this test, the torque or power of the fore and aft propellers was not equalized, and the rotational speed of each propeller was kept constant. However, the fore and aft propellers could be controlled independently, allowing operation with only the fore or aft propellers in case of a failure.

For all tests, the propulsor was operated at low speed prior to towing to confirm rotation, and then the towing speed and propulsor rotational speed were increased simultaneously. Similarly, when stopping the towing carriage, the towing speed and propulsor rotational speed were decreased simultaneously to avoid excessive load on the five-component force/torque sensor. Additionally, the towing speed profile in the test run was adjusted each time so that the measurement section was the same in all tests after the towing speed and the propeller rotational speed were stable.

The test results were evaluated using dimensionless characteristic quantities, equations (1) to (9), and the efficiency evaluation method is summarized in Figure 16.

Figure 14. Tank test arrangement

Figure 15. Control system configuration

Read	: Measured value
Blue	: Parameter value
Green	: Calculated value

System efficiency

$$\eta_s = \frac{T \cdot V_p}{P} = \frac{Q_m \cdot \omega}{P} \times \frac{T \cdot V_p}{Q_m \cdot \omega}$$

η_m	η_p	T: Total thrust	V _p : Towing speed
Motor efficiency	Propeller efficiency	P: Motor input power	Q _m : Motor torque
		ω: Whirl Velocity	

Figure 16. Efficiency evaluation method

9 Tank Test Results

The tests were conducted of the following four items:

Bollard Test: To evaluate the bollard pull/push performance when mounted on tugboats.

The propulsor was mounted in the tank via the towing carriage, and the propeller was operated to evaluate the propulsor thrust and torque.

Propulsion Performance Test: To evaluate the propulsion performance.

The propulsor was mounted to the towing carriage and towed while rotating the propeller to evaluate the propulsor thrust and torque.

Oblique Towing Test: To evaluate oblique performance assuming steering with an azimuth mechanism.

The propulsor was mounted at an angle to the forward direction of the towing carriage and towed while rotating the propeller to evaluate the axial force which is parallel to the propulsor rotating shaft, the lateral force which is perpendicular to the rotating shaft, the yaw moment around the upper strut, and propeller torque.

Long-term Health Test: To evaluate the health of motor cooling using the direct water-cooling system.

The propulsor was operated for a long time in the bollard condition, and motor temperature changes were measured to confirm the effectiveness of the direct water-cooling system.

9.1 Bollard Test and Propulsion Performance Test

The results of the bollard test are shown in Figure 17, and the results of the propulsion performance test are shown in Figure 18. The bollard test results show the input power and total thrust at various operating rotational speeds of 200 rpm. The propulsion performance test results were obtained at several towing speeds at the rated rotational speed of 246 rpm. However, due to the limitations of the test equipment, measurements under high thrust conditions could not be taken, so tests were also conducted at 200 rpm to measure characteristics over a wider range. The figure also shows the ideal efficiency obtained from momentum theory and the efficiency of a conventional nozzle propeller [6] (excluding housing and struts) and an open propeller [7]. However, since bearing losses could not be measured in the tank tests, the measurement results of the CR-RDP include bearing losses. The propulsion efficiency at the design operating point was 61.2%. The adoption of contra-rotating propellers reduced the swirl velocity in the outflow of propeller and confirmed higher efficiency over a wide operating range than conventional nozzle propellers. Additionally, although the efficiency at the design operating point was lower compared to open propellers, the efficiency was higher over a wide operating range, including high propeller loading coefficient. This is because the thrust of the duct increases due to the suction effect of the propeller at high propeller loading coefficient operating points and compensates for the decrease in propeller efficiency. The CFD results showed an efficiency of 65%, which is higher than the experimental results. Possible reasons include the fact that bearing losses were not considered, wave generation occurred despite the presence of an open boat, and the difficulty of accurately predicting the suction effect of the duct. In recent years, tugboats and short-distance coastal vessels used in ports, where the application of electric propulsors is being considered, generally have frequent acceleration and deceleration, and the advantage of high efficiency in high propeller loading coefficient operating points can be utilized. Additionally, for other vessels, adopting smaller propulsors at the design stage can increase the freedom of hull shape and internal layout.

Figure 19 shows a comparison of the ratio of the power of the fore propeller to the total power when the rotational speed of the fore and aft propellers is equal and the propeller loading coefficient is changed. As the propeller loading coefficient increases, the load of the aft propeller increases. This is because as the propeller loading coefficient increases, the axial velocity decreases, the swirl velocity of the outflow flow from the fore propeller increases relatively, and then the angle of attack of the aft propeller increases. This phenomenon can also be explained by the velocity triangle. Since the work increase at the outflow of the fore propeller and the work increase at the inflow of the aft propeller are balanced, and only the load increase at the outflow of the aft propeller remains, the work of the aft propeller is supposed to increase. The work of the aft propeller is larger at the design point. It is considered that this is caused by the problem of CFD which cannot properly estimate the swirl wake field of the fore propeller. In actual operation, it is often operated under high propeller loading conditions such as bollard and acceleration, and it has been found that it is necessary to provide a margin for the power supply to the aft propeller motor.

Figure 17. Result of bollard test

Figure 18. Propulsion efficiency

Figure 19. Power balance of fore/aft propeller

9.2 Oblique Towing Test

The results of the oblique towing test are shown in Figure 20. The rotational speed was fixed at 150 rpm, and the characteristics were plotted against the advance coefficient J when the yaw angle was varied. Due to the limitations of the test equipment, the measurement range was reduced under large yaw angle conditions. However, the main characteristics were sufficiently captured, and this limitation is not considered to have a significant impact on the overall evaluation. The lateral force was not generated at zero-yaw angle but increased as the yaw angle increased. When the yaw angle was increased to 30 degrees, K_Fx increased rapidly. This is considered to be due to flow separation at the duct leading edge, which reduced the inflow speed to the propeller and consequently increased the propeller thrust. It was also found that the side force increased with the advance speed, mainly due to the lift force generated by the duct and struts. It is considered that the lateral force would continue to increase up to the stall point of the struts and other components.

Figure 20. Result of oblique test (N = 150 rpm)

9.3 Long-term Health Test

For the long-term health test, the temperature rise of the motor was measured when operated under the bollard condition for 30 minutes. Thermocouples were installed inside the motor and on the gap flow path between the rotor and stator of the motor, and the temperature change over time was measured. Figure 21 shows the temperature change on the stator of the motor and the fixed side of the gap flow path of the aft propeller when operating at 150 rpm. The motor temperature rise was within 1 °C, and it stabilized in about 10 minutes. Based on these test results, the temperature rise at maximum power was estimated to be less than 3.5 °C. The allowable temperature for the motor coil is 180 °C, and the effectiveness of the direct water-cooling system adopted in this propulsor was confirmed.

Figure 21. Temperature change of motor

10 Conclusion

In this study, new concept propulsor, the Contra-Rotating Rim-Driven Propulsor (CR-RDP), was designed, manufactured and tested. The conclusions obtained from this study are as follows:

- Both the motor and the propeller are rotating machines, and the diameter, axial length, and rotational speed are important design variables. In RDPs, these three main design variables must be shared between the motor and the propeller. Therefore, a system for simultaneously designing the motor and the propeller was constructed, and the system efficiency was optimized under the required constraint conditions.
- The detailed design was carried out based on the above design system. The contra rotating propeller was designed so that the rotational speed and power of the fore and aft propellers are equal at the design point to improve efficiency. At the same time, the divided structure of the duct was examined from the viewpoint of the manufacturability.
- As a result of the bollard test and propulsion performance test with the prototype CR-RDP, it was confirmed that the propeller efficiency at the design operating point was about 2% higher than that of the nozzle propeller. Especially, the difference became larger at the high propeller loading coefficient operating point. In addition, it was found that the efficiency at the design operating point was lower than that of the open propeller, but the efficiency was higher at a wide operating range such as the operating point with the high propeller loading coefficient operating point.
- As a result of the long-term health test, it was confirmed that the motor temperature rise was suppressed to less than 4 °C even in the long-term operation, and the motor was sufficiently cooled. This result demonstrated the effectiveness of the direct water-cooling system.

The tank tests of the CR-RDP confirmed that the propulsor operated appropriately and achieved the required performance. Since the efficiency is high at the high propeller loading coefficient operating point, further consideration will be given to installing this propulsor on vessels that can benefit from this advantage.

D_p	Propeller diameter [m]	D_m	Motor diameter [m]
n	Rotational speed [rps]		
P	Motor input power [W]		
T	Total thrust [N]	Q	Propeller torque [N]
F_x	Axial force [N]	F_y	Side force [N]
M_z	Turning moment [N m]		
ρ	Water density [kg/m ³]	I	Submersion depth [m]
V_p	Towing speed [m/s]		
J	Advance coefficient [-]		

$$J = \frac{V_p}{nD} \quad (1)$$

K_T	Thrust coefficient [-]	K_Q	Torque coefficient [-]
	$K_T = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D_p^4}$		$K_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho n^2 D_p^5}$

$$K_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho n^2 D_p^5} \quad (3)$$

K_{F_x}	Axial force coefficient [-]	K_{F_y}	Side force coefficient [-]
	$K_{F_x} = \frac{F_x}{\rho n^2 D_p^4}$		$K_{F_y} = \frac{F_y}{\rho n^2 D_p^4}$

$$K_{F_y} = \frac{F_y}{\rho n^2 D_p^4} \quad (5)$$

K_{M_z}	Turning moment coefficient [-]		
	$K_{M_z} = \frac{M_z}{\rho n^2 D_p^5}$		

$$(6)$$

CT	Propeller loading coefficient [-]		
	$CT = \frac{T}{0.5 \times \rho V_p^2 \times \frac{1}{4} \pi D_p^2}$		

$$(7)$$

η_p	Propulsion efficiency [-]	η_m	Motor efficiency [-]
	$\eta_p = \frac{J}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{K_T}{K_Q} = \frac{\eta_s}{\eta_m}$		(Measured by motor unit test)

$$(8)$$

η_s	System efficiency [-]		
	$\eta_s = \frac{T \cdot V_p}{P}$		

$$(9)$$

References

- [1] Ludwig Kort. Electrically powered propeller, *German Patent* DE688114C, 1936
- [2] Blarcom, Bill Van et al. The Commercial Rim-Driven Permanent Magnet Motor Propulsor Pod, *Ship Production Symposium*, Boston MA, USA, Sept. Vol. 25. 2002.
- [3] Huyer, Stephen A. and Amanda Dropkin. Integrated motor/propulsor duct optimization for increased vehicle and propulsor performance, *Journal of fluids engineering* 133.4 ,2011.
- [4] Steven Fletcher and Robert Hayes. Are rim-driven propulsors the future? *The Naval Architect*, July/Aug 2017.
- [5] Shen, Yang, et al. Design of novel shaftless pump-jet propulsor for multi-purpose long-range and high-speed autonomous underwater vehicle, *IEEE transactions on magnetics* 52.7, 2016.
- [6] J. D. von Manen. Non-conventional Propulsion Devices, *Proc. of the 2nd Symposium on Marine Propellers (The Society of Naval Architects of Japan)*, 1971
- [7] W. P. A. van Lammeren, et al.: The Wageningen B-Screw Series, *Transactions of The Society of Naval Architects and Marine Engineering*, pp. 269-317, Vol 77, 1969